

Triethanolamine Complexes of Cobalt (II), Nickel (II) and Copper (II) Sulphates

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1 : 2 complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) sulphates with triethanolamine (TEA) have been isolated and their magnetic and spectral characteristics have been examined. Each TEA is bonded to the metal atom through a nitrogen and two oxygen atoms thus giving a pseudooctahedral geometry for the metal.

IN its metal complexes, triethanolamine (TEA, $N(CH_2CH_2OH)_3$) could function as mono, di, tri and even quadridentate ligand. It could also form metal complexes by the deprotonation of one or two of its hydroxy groups¹. Only recently has interest been shown on the structural aspects of the solid complexes of triethanolamine²⁻⁴. We report here the preparation, spectral and magnetic characteristics, X-ray powder data and thermal behaviour of TEA complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) sulphates.

Experimental

All the complexes were prepared by the addition of TEA to the methanol solutions of metal(II) sulphates in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The respective complexes precipitated out immediately and were filtered, washed with acetone and dried. The complexes were insoluble in the common organic solvents and underwent dissociation in water. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature and the magnetic moments were calculated after applying diamagnetic corrections from Figgis and Lewis⁵. The analytical data together with the magnetic moments are given in Table 1. The X-ray powder patterns were taken using CuK_{α} radiation and the d_{hkl} values are given in Table 2. The solid state electronic spectra were recorded on a Cary 14 recording spectrophotometer. Leitz spectrophotometer was employed for infrared spectral studies of the complexes in the range 4000-420 cm^{-1} . The thermal analysis was carried out on a recording Stanton thermobalance in air at a linear rate of heating of 6°C per min.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray powder patterns of the complexes (see Table 2) suggest that Cu and Ni complexes are isomorphous whereas, $Co(TEA)_2SO_4$ is of different type.

The magnetic moments of the complexes strongly indicate the octahedral coordination for Co(II) and Ni(II). The electronic spectral measurements on Co(II) compounds have often been used to assign stereochemistries⁶. The spectral peaks observed at 21.7, 18.5 (sh) and 8.3 kK are respectively assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ of octahedral Co(II). The spectrum of $Ni(TEA)_2SO_4$ showed three bands at 27.0, 17.2 and 11.1 kK which are assigned ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ transitions respectively and indicate the octahedral geometry. $Cu(TEA)_2SO_4$ complex showed three bands at 27.0, 14.4 and 10.0 kK. Neither the magnetic data nor the spectral data could definitely give the correct stereochemistry of the Cu(II) complex. However, since X-ray powder patterns of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes are similar, it is probable that the stereochemistry of copper(II) is somewhat similar to nickel(II) though Jahn-Teller distortions would still be present.

As the complexes were insoluble in many of the common solvents, conductivity studies could not be made to find out the bonding of the sulphate group in the complex. However, the infrared spectra of the complexes showed a strong band around 615 cm^{-1} which is assigned to ν_4SO_4 of T_d symmetry. Due to the coupling of C-C, C-O and C-N stretching and bending modes of TEA, several bands were observed

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA

Complex	Colour	Found %			Required %			μ_{eff} B.M.
		N	S	M	N	S	M	
$[Co(TEA)_2]SO_4$	pink	6.32	6.93	13.2	6.18	7.07	13.0	4.83
$[Ni(TEA)_2]SO_4$	sky blue	6.26	6.88	12.8	6.18	7.08	12.9	3.26
$[Cu(TEA)_2]SO_4$	green	6.04	6.85	13.3	6.12	7.00	13.9	1.92

in the region 900–1200 cm^{-1} thus $\nu_3\text{SO}_4$ band could not be exactly identified. Bands around 3400 and 3100 cm^{-1} are assigned to the -OH stretching frequencies, the former due to coordinated and the latter due to uncoordinated -OH groups in TEA.

bonded to four of oxygens and two nitrogen atoms of the two TEA molecules. The infrared frequencies observed around 600 and 550 cm^{-1} indicate the contributions from M-N and M-O stretching modes as has been reported by Dotson *et al.*⁷

TABLE 2. X-RAY POWDER PHOTOGRAPH DATA (d_{hkl} IN Å.)

[Co(TEA) ₂]SO ₄	[Ni(TEA) ₂]SO ₄	[Cu(TEA) ₂]SO ₄
8.54(s)	5.60(s)	5.65(s)
6.16(m)	4.29(s)	4.27(s)
5.19(s)	3.69(m)	3.71(m)
4.13(w)	3.39(m)	3.41(m)
4.03(w)	3.19(m)	3.20(m)
3.64(s)	2.92(s)	2.91(s)
3.45(m)	2.77(w)	2.76(w)
3.38(m)	2.49(w)	2.49(w)
3.16(s)	2.34(m)	2.34(m)
2.97(m)	2.15(m)	2.15(m)
2.61(m)	2.11(w)	2.09(w)
2.45(m)	1.88(w)	1.88(w)
2.37(m)		
2.18(m)		

The splitting of CO stretching frequency (1050 and 1000 cm^{-1}) in the complexes confirms non-equivalence of OH group in the complexes. As the sulphate group is shown to be ionic by the infrared spectra to satisfy 6 coordination, the metal ion has to be

The thermal behaviour of the complexes indicate that they start decomposing around 180°C and they give the metal oxides as the end product at about 750°C. Work is in progress on the isolation and characterization of the intermediate products formed during the thermal decompositions at different temperature ranges.

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